

Table 1. Performance of composites in station trials, Moor Plantation, Ibadan, Nigeria, 1978.

Group	Designation	Cross	Average height (m)	Days to maturity	Panicles/m ²	Drought score	Blast score	Grain yield (t/ha)
a	FAROX298	Crosses of FARO 11	111	120	132	3	4	1.90
b	FAROX299	Crosses of IRAT1069m-1-2 with other varieties [excluding (a)]	105	119	144	2	2	2.12
c	FAROX300	Crosses of E425 and others excluding (a) and (b)	112	120	122	3	4	2.00
d	FAROX301	Crosses of OS4 and others excluding (a), (b), and (c)	109	120	132	3	4	1.90
e	FAROX302	Crosses of FARO 25 and others excluding (a), (b), (c), and (d)	108	123	132	3	4	2.00
f	FARO 11 (check)	—	111	120	132	4	3	2.00
g	Mixture (check)	Physical mixture of all parents in equal proportions	113	120	122	5	3	2.00
LSD	—	—	ns	ns	ns	—	—	ns
CV%	—	—	8.6	—	14.8	—	—	16.4

phenotypic acceptance and resistance to drought. During 1982 season, when total rainfall for the last 40 d of crop growth was 60 mm, FAROX299 produced the highest grain yield.

In 1984, the composite outyielded FARO 11 at three sites of a multilocation trial and produced as much yield as FARO 11 in one location (Table 2). At Onne, a high-rainfall area, FAROX299 showed resistance to sheath blight and leaf scald.

Table 2. Performance of FAROX299 in multilocation trials in Nigeria, 1984.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
FAROX299	3.08	1.10	2.30	1.00	1.97	1.88
FARO 11 (check)	3.42	0.65	2.17	2.23	1.76	2.04
ITA117 (check)	2.35	0.25	1.58	1.48	1.74	1.48

^aLocation 1 = NCRI, Ibadan; 2 = IITA, Ibadan; 3 = Ikenne; 4 = Amakama, and 5 = Onne (IITA).

In 1986, the composite was recommended by the Nationally Coordinated Research Project for

release as a commercial variety for Nigeria. □

Paicos 1, a promising new rice for Manipur

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Paicos 1 is a promising semidwarf rice from a cross between local Phouren and RP8-9. It has wide adaptability to

irrigated, rainfed lowland, and transplanted conditions. It is photoperiod insensitive, matures in 135-140 d, and has high yield potential and stability. It outyielded popular rice varieties Punshi and Jaya (Table 1). The grains are long, slender, and translucent with local consumer

preference similar to that for Punshi.

Field trials during Jul-Aug and Nov-Dec 1981-84 showed high resistance to leaf and nodal blast and false smut (Table 2). □

Table 1. Performance of Paicos 1 in Imphal District, Manipur, India, 1981-85.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Panicles/m ²	Milling %	Length: width	Kernel elongation (mm)	Cooking quality
Paicos 1	6.2	138	290	68	3.44	1.98	Good
Punshi	5.9	135	291	65	3.10	1.83	Good
Jaya	5.8	138	290	70	2.86	1.76	Fair
CD at 5%	0.2						
CV%	9.0						

Table 2. Field reaction of Paicos 1 to blast and false smut, Manipur, India, 1981-85.

Variety	Reaction ^a			Rating ^a
	Leaf blast	Nodal blast	False smut	
Paicos 1	0-1	0-1	0-1	R
Punshi	2-3	2-3	2-3	S
Jaya	2-3	2-3	2-3	S

^aScored on the *Standard evaluation system rice* scale. R = resistant, S = susceptible.